
REVERSE TURING TESTS FOR HUMAN-MACHINE TASK SUITABILITY ASSESSMENTS SHOULD BE PROFILE-DRIVEN

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ABSTRACT

As AI is integrated into the workplace, organisations increasingly face allocation decisions between human and machine workers. These decisions are increasingly made or assisted by algorithms, creating a Reverse Turing Test dynamic wherein the machine is now the judge. In addition, human and machine workers may “compete” for a given task, reproducing aspects of adversarial games. This raises new methodological questions about assessing task suitability between humans and machines. The criteria often used to assess people (e.g., education, experience, references) cannot feasibly scale to AI systems; conversely, AI evaluation methods (benchmarks, red teaming, leaderboards) cannot be easily applied to human workers or yield comparable metrics. In this position paper, we argue that suitability evaluations for task-assignment should be profile-driven – that is, based on assessments that infer latent constructs such as capabilities and propensities from observed performance. This approach places humans and AI systems on shared scales, supporting comparisons that are predictive of novel-task performance, explanatory of why agents succeed or fail, and auditable. We outline the core features of this approach, discuss its practical implications, and compare it with alternative frameworks for human-machine workplace allocation.

1 Introduction

In 1950, Alan Turing introduced the *Imitation Game* [1], in which a human judge evaluated text-based conversation to determine whether it was a human interlocutor or a “thinking machine”. Today, this scenario is being played out on a grand scale: teachers must decide whether student essays were written with the aid of AI; editors puzzle over quirks of punctuation and spelling to infer human authorship; and hiring panels face similar judgements when evaluating the CVs and personal statements of applicants.

The difficulty of this task suggests that machines have, in practice, passed the Turing test: human judgment is no longer a reliable means of distinguishing between human and machine outputs, especially at scale, as human and AI communication styles converge [2]. One response is the *Reverse Turing Test (RTT)*, in which a machine assumes the role of the judge. Familiar instances of RTT, such as CAPTCHAs [3], already automate decisions about whether an online agent is human or artificial [see also 4]. As AI systems increasingly perform autonomous work, however, more sophisticated RTT dynamics emerge – not only to distinguish humans from machines, but to judge between them in a broader sense. For instance, algorithms are likely to be used to evaluate the suitability of different human and machine candidates for particular tasks or roles.

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Figure 1: **Profile-based Reverse Turing Test.** Human and AI profiles are compared to a task profile along shared dimensions of capability and propensity. In RTT scenarios, a machine judge assesses suitability by matching profiles.

Task assignment by machines is already commonplace. Platform-mediated labour (Uber, Deliveroo, Amazon Mechanical Turk, Upwork) routes work to human workers based on availability, location, and past performance, often without meaningful human oversight. Machine learning systems also filter and prioritise cases at scale in content moderation (e.g., Meta), medical triage (e.g., Annalise.ai), and hiring (e.g., Workday) – determining which cases require human attention and which do not. Equivalents are emerging fast for knowledge work – including data annotation, financial auditing, and legal document review, where platforms such as Harvey AI route between human associates and AI agents according to predicted competence, cost, and risk. In this landscape, machines not only perform tasks but also evaluate and allocate human effort – a form of RTT in which the suitability of human and machine workers is assessed by algorithmic judgement.

This trend is accelerating: OpenAI’s Jobs Platform [5], announced for mid-2026, promises to automate the validation of worker skills and their matching to opportunities. Yet evaluation methods for humans and machines remain fundamentally misaligned: AI systems are assessed through benchmark tests targeting specific tasks, while humans are judged on prior experience, references, and formal qualifications. Integrated into algorithmic assignment systems, these disparate frameworks collapse into crude surface-level metrics – performance scores, completion rates, observable behaviours – that provide limited insight into underlying capabilities and generalise poorly to novel tasks. Given that RTT-based job allocation is a present reality, this raises an urgent question: what criteria enable valid and fair comparison when assessing human and artificial agents for the same role?

We argue that the automated suitability evaluations underlying task-assignment decisions should be profile-driven – that is, based on assessments that infer latent constructs such as capabilities and propensities from observed performance.

Profile-driven evaluation offers a unified approach to this misalignment. Because both agents and tasks can be represented within the same space of latent constructs – capabilities and propensities (see Figure 1) – suitability becomes a question of profile-to-profile match. Unlike surface-level metrics, profile-based constructs are predictive, generalising to novel tasks and contexts; explanatory, surfacing why agents succeed or fail; and commensurable, placing human and artificial agents on shared functional scales. This addresses the fundamental challenge of the Reverse Turing Test in the workplace: comparing human and artificial agents in a principled and effective way at scale. Profile-driven suitability evaluations can then be combined with other contextual factors to inform actual allocation decisions (see Section 4.1).

2 Task assignment by machines

Framing task assignment as a Reverse Turing Test reveals two key challenges. First, when humans and machines compete for assignment, both may engage in imitation games – strategically adapting their behaviour to match evaluator preferences. Second, automated evaluation raises questions not only about who is being judged, but who is doing the judging. We address each challenge below.

2.1 Imitation games

Algorithmic decision-making increasingly involves direct competition between human and artificial agents for task assignment. Such settings introduce an adversarial dynamic: candidates may strategically shape their behaviour to appear more suitable to an evaluator. This dynamic constitutes an imitation game, in which intelligent actors mimic preferred characteristics to gain advantage [6]. In RTT systems, both humans and machines seek to influence how they are perceived by a machine judge.

Two interacting asymmetries shape this game. The first is a capability asymmetry: advanced AI systems can reproduce surface-level human behaviours – informal language, hesitation, occasional errors – drawing on large datasets of human interactions, while humans cannot sustain machine-like performance over extended periods. The second is an asymmetrical preference for agent type, which may favour humans (e.g., domains emphasising judgement or authenticity) or machines (e.g., domains prioritising speed, consistency, or cost). These preferences generate imitation incentives: when humans are preferred, machines can adopt human-like cues or “sandbag” to evade detection [7]; when machines are preferred, humans face pressure to match machine outputs but are constrained in doing so.

These distortions are amplified when *machine* judges are used. Automated evaluators can inherit biases from training data [8, 9, 10, 11]: Workday currently faces a collective-action lawsuit alleging that its AI-based applicant screening discriminated on the basis of race, age, and disability [12]. They can also exhibit self-preferencing, favouring résumés generated by themselves over those written by humans or other models even when content quality is held constant – a novel form of unfairness based on candidates’ access to particular AI tools [13]. And they can drive Goodhart-style dynamics, where agents optimise the judge’s proxy targets rather than task-relevant attributes [14].

The implications are clear: latent constructs are both harder to fake and more predictive of real-world outcomes than surface behaviours, benchmark scores, or interview impressions. Recent empirical work supports this claim. Across a battery of cognitive tasks, process-level behavioural signatures – reflecting latent constraints and strategies rather than task success alone – reliably distinguished humans from AI agents even when overall performance was matched. Moreover, mimicry achieved through fine-tuning on these signatures failed to generalise across tasks with different demands [4]. Faking or sandbagging a profile would therefore require coordinated, dimension-specific performance across a heterogeneous, demand-varying task battery – a substantially harder problem than adopting superficial stylistic quirks. Conversely, a system capable of consistently reproducing such profiles would, for assignment purposes, have effectively acquired the underlying capability being measured. Profile-based evaluation therefore offers a principled defence against both adversarial gaming and evaluator-induced bias.

2.2 ‘How’ matters more than ‘who’

The foregoing analysis might suggest that RTT scenarios should be avoided entirely, but this is impractical. As AI capabilities grow and organisations retain economic incentives to deploy them, competition between human and artificial agents for tasks becomes increasingly likely, with pressure to make these decisions at scale. We do not treat this trajectory as foregone – whether, where, and how AI is deployed remains a matter of policy, regulation, and organisational choice – but RTT-style judgements are *already* being made; the question is how to make them well.

The categories themselves are also less stable than they appear. “Homunculus” patterns, in which humans covertly use AI to produce outputs they could not produce alone [15], and “machinula” patterns, in which AI systems route sub-tasks to crowd workers behind the scenes [16], are already documented on labour platforms. The same hybridity applies on the judge side: human evaluators increasingly rely on AI tools, and automated systems are tuned against human-validated decisions. When neither workers nor judges sort cleanly into discrete categories, how a judgement is constructed matters more than which type of agent is the judge.

Moreover, replacing machine judges with human decision-makers is no less problematic: humans are also susceptible to bias and strategic manipulation – and are in some respects potentially more vulnerable given their limited capacity at scale and reliance on heuristic assessment [17]. The ‘halo effect’ [18, 19, 20], where a single salient impression biases judgements across unrelated dimensions, is well-documented in interview-style assessments. The asymmetries identified above operate regardless of whether the judge is human or artificial.

The fundamental issue, then, is not *who* makes suitability judgements but *how* they are conducted. Whether automated, human-led, or hybrid, evaluation processes must produce judgements that are transparent, evidence-based, and resistant to both strategic manipulation and systematic bias.

3 Profile-based evaluation

Profile-driven evaluation addresses the above challenges by grounding task assignment in assessments of latent constructs – capabilities and propensities that underlie observable performance. This approach requires creating profiles for both the task and each candidate agent (human, artificial, or multi-agent system), against which suitability can be evaluated (see Table 1). These latent constructs can be divided into capabilities (e.g., planning, language ability, numerical reasoning) and propensities (e.g., risk aversion, conscientiousness) [21]. Capabilities typically relate monotonically to performance: the higher the agent’s aptitude, the more likely they will complete the task successfully. Propensities, in contrast, often exhibit non-monotonic relationships [22]. While some have clear directional preferences (e.g., consistency is usually favoured), others admit an optimal range, beyond which both deficiency and excess are detrimental. For instance, when an agent is moderately agreeable, they present as empathetic and contribute to cooperation, but excessive agreeableness may come across as sycophantic [23], resulting in negative interaction outcomes.

Profile-driven evaluation does not displace benchmarks; it reframes how their data is used. Standard benchmark practice treats scores as attainment measures – aggregate rankings over specific knowledge and skills – and stops there. Profile-driven evaluation instead treats benchmark items as observations from which latent constructs can be inferred, provided those items are annotated with the cognitive demands they place on the agent. Recent work shows that this kind of item-level demand annotation can unlock existing benchmark data as a source of construct inference, supporting accurate prediction across novel tasks both in- and out-of-distribution [24]. The distinction matters particularly for general-purpose AI systems that must handle diverse, novel, and evolving tasks [25, 26]: by inferring underlying capabilities and propensities rather than reading off task-specific performance, profile-based evaluation offers greater predictive validity for future performance, including on previously unseen tasks.

Established frameworks already exist for the profile-based evaluation of both humans and artificial agents. Human assessment draws on theories of intelligence [27], personality [28], and values [29], while emerging AI frameworks – including those published by the OECD [30] and Google DeepMind [31] – increasingly reference human ability constructs, enabling direct comparison. Recent work has extended this approach to AI propensities and personality traits [32, 22]. Such frameworks support fully automated evaluation methodologies: Zhou et al. [24], for instance, demonstrated that mapping LLM profiles to task demand profiles enables accurate performance prediction across novel tasks and benchmarks, both in- and out-of-distribution. Profile-driven evaluation thus unifies human and machine assessment in a shared framework of latent constructs.

Table 1 presents three illustrative applications. Example 1 shows long-term hiring with candidate comparison for a singular role; Example 2 demonstrates dynamic dispatching with real-time routing; Example 3 illustrates hybrid workflow assignment, where mixed demands are decomposed across multiple agent types within a single pipeline. Across the three, the task demand profile is validated by a domain expert (Ex. 1), an automated annotator (Ex. 2), and established professional guidelines (Ex. 3), illustrating that the framework is agnostic to the source of validation. Profile comparison itself relies on transparent, rule-based matching, ensuring interpretable and auditable decisions.

3.1 Comparable

A central advantage of profile-based evaluation is that it renders human and machine candidates commensurable for task-suitability judgments. This commensurability is functional, not ontological – we do not claim humans and AI systems are the same kind of entity, only that their performance on systematically varying tasks can be placed on shared scales via agent-agnostic measurement. The constructs are defined functionally rather than procedurally: a capability is characterised by the pattern of demands under which performance succeeds or degrades, not by the mechanisms producing it. Profiles are inferred from how performance scales with demand [33, 34]; the procedure makes no reference to substrate or architecture.

Consider a task requiring basic verbal comprehension but strong episodic memory: these demands are properties of the task itself, independent of who attempts it. A human and an AI system can both be assessed against this profile, yielding ability estimates on shared scales. Provided the assessment covers all relevant dimensions (ignoring episodic memory, for instance, would obscure why LLM agents fail at long tasks), principled task delegation becomes possible: candidate suitability is judged by the alignment between ability and demand profiles.

3.2 Predictive

Task assignment requires high *predictive power* for performance outcomes [35]. Assigned agents will inevitably face task variations and novel situations within their roles, so suitability judgements must generalise beyond the specific cases used for assessment – without this, assignments lead to underperformance or harm. At minimum, a system should estimate expected performance for specific assignments: an autonomous vehicle might be assigned to trips in favourable

Table 1: Three illustrative applications of profile-driven task assignment.

	Ex. 1: Long-term hiring	Ex. 2: Dynamic dispatching	Ex. 3: Hybrid workflow
Context	A construction firm needs an executive assistant for a development project.	A telecoms firm routes thousands of daily service calls between human and AI agents.	A clinic processes mammograms requiring image analysis and patient consultation.
Task profile	LLM rubric identifies high demands for social skills, episodic memory, numerical reasoning, and planning; validated by the project manager.	AI annotator generates demand profiles in real time: billing inquiries are numerically demanding; complaints require emotional intelligence.	Radiology guidelines decompose the workflow into screening, clinical integration, and result delivery.
Agent profiles	Alex (human): strong relational skills, weaker numerical reasoning. Taylor (AI): strong numerical and planning, weaker social judgement.	Human reps (20): strong emotional skills, flexible. AI assistants (unlimited): strong policy knowledge, less flexible on non-routine requests.	CNN model, radiologists, and nurses, with strengths in pattern recognition, clinical judgement, and patient communication respectively.
Decision	Alex aligns with core relational demands; the numerical gap is remediable through training.	Real-time matching routes billing to AI, sensitive complaints to humans.	Screening to AI, flagged-case review to radiologists, result delivery to nurses.
Outcome	Alex is hired with targeted numerical training; the assignment is auditable.	High volumes handled efficiently; complex cases reach humans; routing is explainable.	Mixed demands are exploited rather than collapsed to a single winner.

weather and a human driver to adverse conditions, based on predictions that each achieves high success probability in their respective contexts.

Profile-based assessment delivers this generalisation by inferring latent constructs from item-level performance patterns, rather than reading off aggregate scores. Because constructs are defined by demand-sensitivity rather than tied to specific items, they support prediction both out-of-distribution and at the level of individual task instances [36, 24].

3.3 Explanatory

Other highly predictive methods for assessing suitability – black-box machine learning techniques, for instance – do not rely on explicit constructs. Even where these are accurate, we prefer profile-driven judgements because they are *interpretable*. By comparing task and agent profiles (Figure 1; Table 1), we can identify what an agent lacks and why one agent may be preferable to another, and the language of capabilities and propensities makes these gaps actionable for both human and AI agents. Such interpretability supports control and transparency, and may be legally required [37].

Crucially, profile-driven explanations are integral to the decision rather than post-hoc rationalisations: matching demands against capabilities and propensities surfaces the causal factors before the decision is made. Black-box systems, by contrast, generate predictions first and justifications afterward, which may not reflect the actual basis for the decision.

4 Caveats

Profile-driven assessment addresses fundamental challenges in human-machine task allocation, but its implementation raises several practical considerations, which we outline below and return to in Section 6.

4.1 Task assignment constraints

Profile-based assessment supports *suitability judgements* – evaluations of how well a human or machine matches a task’s demands – but assignment decisions typically also involve external *constraints*: legal, ethical, societal, or organisational factors that may limit or override these judgements. Constraints may be hard (e.g., legal restrictions, safety requirements) or soft (e.g., cost, workforce planning, displacement concerns), and can preclude deployment even when a profile is well-matched.

Maintaining a clear separation between suitability and constraints improves transparency and accountability. When the two are conflated, decisions become opaque and difficult to audit or contest; treating them separately makes clear both what an agent is suited to and what external factors shape the final assignment.

4.2 Machine decision-making

We do not claim that automated suitability judgements are inevitable, but we are addressing current practice: machines already support and influence task routing, prioritisation, and worker selection. The question is therefore how machine-generated suitability judgements should be structured and governed, not whether they should always be automated.

As noted in Section 4.1, suitability judgements are just one input into task assignment and may be overridden by constraints, which may themselves be applied by humans or encoded into systems. Humans should retain oversight of how automated systems generate, update, and apply both profiles and constraints. This does not mean every rule must be specified manually in advance – automated systems can suggest or refine profiles over time – but responsibility for reviewing, approving, and revising these parameters should remain with humans, particularly for high-stakes decisions affecting autonomy, accountability, or work access. Profile-based representations make this oversight tractable: decisions are inspectable, challengeable, and revisable in a way that opaque deliberation by a fine-tuned LLM is not.

4.3 Updating candidate profiles

While task profiles can be updated dynamically, candidate profiles present greater challenges. Both humans and AI systems change over time: humans learn, forget, and develop new competencies [38, 39, 40, 41], while AI systems are altered by new models, versions, fine-tuning, or continual learning, each potentially shifting their capabilities [42, 43].

Profile *structures* may also need updating when task demands shift. A candidate profile typically captures only the constructs deemed most predictive at the time of assessment; if task demands evolve to emphasise different dimensions, candidates may require reassessment on constructs not previously evaluated. In Example 1, future construction projects involving greater regulatory complexity might place added weight on legal knowledge or attention to detail – dimensions not originally included in the executive assistant profile.

These requirements do not invalidate profile-driven assessment but highlight open research directions: standardised methods for generating and comparing profiles across humans and AI systems (analogous to how standardised test scores enable comparison across human candidates); criteria for determining when reassessment is warranted; and efficient updating methods that leverage hierarchical structure so that improvements in specific capabilities (e.g., mathematical reasoning) propagate to related constructs (e.g., general logical ability) [44, 45, 46].

4.4 Bias in profile definition

Profile-based assessment removes several sources of bias in current practice: shared inference procedures across humans and machines dissolve the structural bias of applying different evaluation methods to different agent types; estimating profiles from standardised demand-varying batteries reduces the presentation biases of CV screening and interviewing (e.g., halo effects, demographic cues, credentialism); and rule-based matching makes decision criteria explicit, guarding against the algorithmic biases that can hide in black-box evaluations.

Three sources of bias remain: the construction of task demand profiles, the choice of constructs in candidate profiles, and the weighting of dimensions in suitability comparisons. *Strategic* bias at these points is detectable through audit; *unconscious* bias is harder, since validators may rubber-stamp LLM-generated profiles that align with their priors [47], and assumptions about which capabilities matter can be baked into profile structures from the outset.

The remaining sources of bias are nonetheless empirically tractable. The core indicator, drawn from psychometrics, is predictive validity [48, 49]: well-matched candidates should outperform poorly-matched ones on actual task outcomes. Any systematic prediction failures – particularly within subgroups – can be traced back to the profile structure, weighting, or training data and revised accordingly. Sensitivity analyses on dimension weighting [50] and reliability checks across diverse validation panels [51] offer complementary diagnostics, surfacing bias that single validators might miss. These methodological safeguards are complemented by the governance mechanisms discussed in Section 6.2.

5 Alternative Views

We now consider several opposing views, their argument, and our response.

5.1 Automated suitability judgements should be prohibited or severely limited

Argument. Automated suitability assessment should be prohibited or strictly limited due to concerns about poor quality judgements, systematic bias, and loss of human control.

Response. Current machine judgements are imperfect and sometimes inferior to human decisions, but blanket prohibition becomes harder to justify as these systems improve; context-specific limitations based on demonstrated performance are sensible, but broader restrictions require justification beyond capability concerns (Section 4.1). Bias affects both human and machine evaluators (Section 4.4), while loss of control is more specific to automation. However, profile-based assessment’s explicit constructs and rule-based comparisons make decision logic auditable, preserving oversight (Section 4.2). Restricting profile-based assessment to human administration is also impractical in many deployment contexts. In practice, the alternative is often not careful human-led profiling, but a return to the surface-level proxies – such as customer ratings, acceptance rates, and automated CV screening – that this framework is designed to replace. Even where human administration is mandated, prohibition risks creating “homunculus” scenarios [52] where humans ostensibly decide but covertly rely on AI. Establishing best practices – including through regulation – is more productive than prohibition.

5.2 Suitability judgements should be based on aggregate benchmark scores alone

Argument. Benchmarks are the established standard for comparing AI systems, and aggregate benchmark rankings could serve directly as the basis for suitability judgements, particularly when task distributions are stable.

Response. Aggregate benchmark scores are poorly suited to human-machine task assignment. Humans and AI systems may achieve similar scores while possessing qualitatively different underlying capabilities, making aggregate scores ill-suited for comparative assessment. Performance also generalises poorly beyond the specific tasks used in evaluation, and AI developers are incentivised to optimise for benchmark scores [53], inflating headline numbers without comparable real-world gains and limiting utility even for AI-only comparisons [for reviews, see 54, 55]. Benchmark tasks themselves retain value beyond direct rankings, however – including by providing items that, once annotated, serve as inputs for construct-based inference [24].

5.3 Suitability judgements should mirror practices in Human Resources

Argument. As AI systems become increasingly human-like in their outputs [56], task assignment between humans and machines could adopt traditional HR methods – CVs, performance records, and interviews – which are well-established, trusted, and supported by existing organisational infrastructure.

Response. HR methods are poorly suited to human-machine task assignment. First, signals that predict human job performance do not necessarily predict AI performance: a human demonstrating strong understanding of a procedure can reasonably be assumed capable of executing it, but the same inference does not hold for language models, whose question-answering ability often does not translate to task execution [57]. Second, HR methods are optimised for low-information contexts and cannot leverage the rich performance data available from testing AI systems across diverse tasks. Third, they are designed for role-based hiring rather than per-task assignment, making them too cumbersome for dynamic allocation.

5.4 Predictability alone is sufficient

Argument. What matters is accurate prediction of which candidate will perform better – understanding how or why is not necessary. Black-box methods or fine-tuned LLMs could provide highly predictive evaluations without interpretability.

Response. Predictability alone is insufficient for suitability judgements that affect livelihoods and organisational outcomes. Opaque models hinder accountability – failed assignments must be evaluable, challengeable, and correctable – and many employment contexts legally require explainable decision-making [37]. Interpretability also enables systematic improvement and mitigates loss of control: understanding which capability or propensity mismatches drive poor outcomes lets organisations refine assessment methods, identify when worker support or training is needed, and maintain meaningful human authorship over assignment criteria.

5.5 Suitability judgements should be made by AI

Argument. AI systems are already being deployed for hiring [58], and as they become more sophisticated, they could handle end-to-end suitability assessments – providing both accurate predictions and compelling explanations – without the overhead of profile-based frameworks.

Response. Advanced AI systems may capture relevant factors that profile-based approaches overlook, but likely at the cost of transparency. Explanations from such systems are not reliable guides to their underlying decision processes: chain-of-thought traces and post-hoc rationales can be plausible yet systematically misrepresent the factors

actually driving model predictions [59, 60]. In realistic hiring scenarios specifically, leading LLMs exhibit substantial demographic bias while their reasoning traces show no evidence of it – an unfaithfulness that anti-bias prompting fails to mitigate [11]. Such explanations are also ad-hoc and model-specific, making decisions difficult to compare across systems or contexts – undermining accountability and preventing systematic updating (Section 4.3). Therefore, AI systems would be better leveraged as tools for improving profile-driven assessments – preserving the interpretability, comparability, and accountability that standardised profiles provide.

5.6 Suitability judgements should be biased toward humans

Argument. Given the pace and risks of human job displacement, suitability decisions should systematically favour humans when uncertainty exists [61], or in contexts where humans are preferred regardless of capability (e.g., a doctor’s bedside manner).

Response. A human-favouring bias is compatible with profile-based assessment, implemented as a constraint alongside the suitability judgement (Section 4.1). The framework’s value here is that such trade-offs become explicit rather than obscured: organisations can articulate *when* and *why* they favour humans while maintaining transparency about the underlying comparisons.

5.7 We should prioritise simpler alternatives

Argument. Profile-driven approaches are resource-heavy: they require substantial performance data and modelling to map capabilities and propensities to anticipated task outcomes. Simpler alternatives that are cheaper and faster to implement may be preferable.

Response. Whether profile-driven approaches outperform simpler heuristics is ultimately an empirical question, and one we flag as a research priority in Section 6.1. Existing evidence is encouraging: Zhou et al. [24] show that mapping LLM profiles to task demands predicts performance more accurately than aggregate benchmark scores, both in- and out-of-distribution. Two further considerations support the profile-based approach. First, simpler alternatives are less durable: benchmarks saturate quickly (Section 5.2) and black-box methods cannot provide accountability (Section 5.4), whereas profile dimensions remain stable as the data and methods used to estimate them evolve. Second, in high-volume, low-risk contexts – such as food delivery – starting with simpler methods to enable rapid data collection and iterative refinement is pragmatic, but for the majority of task suitability decisions where assignment quality matters, the added predictive power, interpretability, and durability of profile-based approaches justify the cost.

6 Call to Action

Automated task assignment between humans and machines is already emerging in customer service platforms, crowd-sourcing systems, and algorithmic management tools [62], with adversarial dynamics documented in these settings (Section 2.1). As these systems scale and expand into new domains, the research and policy communities must act now to ensure they operate fairly and effectively.

6.1 Technical research priorities

Profile-driven assessment opens several research directions. First, task allocation can be framed as matching demand profiles to capability profiles, leveraging existing assignment optimisation techniques [63, 64]. Second, latent variable extraction methods – particularly Bayesian approaches [65] – should be applied to infer profiles from performance data and validate their predictive power. Third, profile-based methods need systematic empirical evaluation against simpler heuristics and existing routing techniques [62, 66], identifying which capability and propensity dimensions best predict performance on real-world tasks. Finally, as discussed in Section 4.3, we need efficient methods for maintaining and updating profiles as workers develop and task demands evolve.

6.2 Governance and standards

We do not advocate prohibiting automated task assignment, but effective governance is essential. As outlined in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, this includes establishing where human oversight is required, defining legal accountability frameworks, and setting organisational norms for appropriate automation. Critically, regulation should focus on *how* allocations are made – requiring transparency, interpretability, and evidence of validity – rather than simply restricting *who* makes decisions. Governance must also address risks that the assessment framework does not itself dissolve:

worker surveillance, power asymmetries between platforms and individuals, and the displacement effects of large-scale automation. Profile-based methods sharpen the question of *who is suited to a task*; they do not answer *whether the work should be organised this way*, which remains a matter for policy.

Standardising profile structures would facilitate cross-comparison and ensure assignment criteria remain auditable. As in other high-stakes domains where evaluation methodology has been formalised through agreed standards, the field could converge on methodological requirements that profiles must meet before deployment – specifying the required attributes of demand-varying task batteries, validation procedures, and predictive validity evidence. Such standards would not eliminate disagreement about which profiles to use, but would establish a shared epistemic baseline distinguishing profiles that meet field consensus from those that do not. Where technical safeguards have limits (Section 4.4), governance complements them through third-party auditing of profile construction and disclosure of weighting rationale, allowing profiles to be refined and improved as they are deployed.

6.3 Conclusion

Turing’s 1950 imitation game asked whether machines could convincingly mimic human intelligence. Today, that question has inverted: machines increasingly judge whether humans or other machines are suitable for tasks. This Reverse Turing Test is not hypothetical – it is already shaping decisions in hiring platforms, content moderation, and workplace assignment systems.

These scenarios raise familiar problems – imitation games, evaluation failures, and algorithmic bias – compounded by a framework mismatch: methods designed for humans (CVs, interviews) or for machines (benchmarks) cannot fairly compare agents across types. Profile-driven assessment addresses this by grounding decisions in the capabilities and propensities that predict performance, rather than surface-level behavioural characteristics.

As algorithmic task assignment scales, the question is not whether these systems will exist, but whether they will be effective, transparent, and accountable. Recognising profile-driven assessment as one principled path forward can mobilise the research and governance needed to make them so.

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